

HOW TO DEVELOP INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE THROUGH EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article is about how to develop intercultural competence through education.

Key words: Informal education, Formal education, Principles of planning, comparison and analysis.

Intercultural education refers to a pedagogy – aims, content, learning processes, teaching methods, syllabus and materials, and assessment – one purpose of which is to develop intercultural competence in learners of all ages in all types of education as a foundation for dialogue and living together.

Intercultural competence can be developed in different ways through different types of education. Three types of education exist and for the purposes of this paper are defined following the Council of Europe.

- Informal education means the lifelong process whereby every individual acquires attitudes, skills and knowledge from the educational influences and resources in his or her own environment and from daily experience and conversation (family, peer group, neighbors, encounters, library, mass media, work, play, etc.). In informal education – for example in what is learnt from parents, carers, peers, journalists and others in one's social environment – intercultural competence is acquired with differing degrees of deliberate activity on the part of parents, carers, peers, journalists and others. Parents, for example, may have a pedagogical approach to developing intercultural competence which is more or less conscious and deliberate, or bring up their children with no deliberate intercultural purpose at all.

- Non-formal education means any planned program of education designed to improve a range of skills and competences outside the formal educational setting, and throughout lifelong learning. In non-formal education – as provided for example by local communities, youth work, adult education and social work – intercultural competence is a pedagogical goal pursued through deliberate inclusion of specific activities for learning.

- Formal education means the structured education and training system that runs from pre-primary and primary through secondary school and on to higher education. It takes place, as a rule, at general or vocational educational institutions and usually leads to certification. In formal education, the pedagogy of intercultural competence involves the planned inclusion of learning outcomes defined in terms of the

components of intercultural competence. In formal education, with its high degree of planning, responsibility for developing intercultural competence in learners reaches across the explicit and the 'hidden' curriculum, and is shared by all teachers albeit to differing degrees.

Each type of education involves a relationship between a 'facilitator of learning' and 'learners'. In informal learning there are, for example, parents and children, or adults learning together, for example politicians, artists, professionals in the media, religious, spiritual or community leaders, work colleagues or fellow students learning from each other; in non-formal education there are, for example, youth workers and young people or trainers and adults; in formal education there are teachers/lecturers and pupils/students.

'Facilitators' usually have intentions or purposes throughout their interaction with those in their charge. Teachers, youth workers and adult education tutors, for example, are trained to plan and design their lessons and activities, and do so in a conscious way, whereas parents may sometimes consciously plan activities for their children, or follow advice from books, or imitate their own parents, or adopt what is customary in their community, or follow practices they see on television, and do so intuitively. In informal learning, where people are constantly learning from each other, they can have the intention, more or less conscious, of influencing others. However, informal learning can also sometimes take place through observation and imitation, without any intentions to influence by the person whose actions are imitated by the learner.

Principles of planning: Planning and pursuing the development of intercultural competence amongst learners is thus important for all facilitators of learning. Some will do so deliberately as a professional task as teachers, youth workers, social workers, for example; others will do so less deliberately, as an inherent aspect of their role as parents, employers, politicians, etc.; and yet others will do so often without any conscious planning or awareness of what they 'teach' by what they do or say.

In most cases there are some principles of planning which are related to the different components of intercultural competence described earlier. Facilitators need to include in their planning:

- Experience: Developing attitudes of respect, curiosity and openness, as well as acquiring knowledge about other cultural orientations and affiliations, are best pursued through directly experiencing how people act, interact and communicate – from their perspective. Facilitators may well provide opportunities for learning through experience, which can be either 'real' or 'imagined'; learners are able to gain experiences, for example, through games, activities, traditional media and social media, through face-to-face interaction with others or through correspondence. Parents may select books for their children or travel with them to other

neighbourhoods, regions and countries; youth workers may organise training events and international meetings for young people; or history teachers may plan dramatic reconstructions or activities that aim to develop multiperspectivity. All of these examples can provide opportunities for challenging one's assumptions through comparison and analysis.

- Comparison: In order to encourage understanding and respect for people who are perceived to have different cultural affiliations from themselves, learners can benefit from exposure to 'difference'. Learners often compare what is unfamiliar with what is familiar and evaluate the unfamiliar as 'bizarre', or as 'worse' and even as 'uncivilised'. Facilitators need to be aware of this kind of 'comparison of value' and replace it with 'comparison for understanding', which involves seeing similarities and differences in a non-judgmental manner and taking the perspective of 'the other' in order to 'see ourselves as others see us'. In other words, learners can be encouraged to develop an understanding of how what is normal for them can be regarded as 'bizarre' or 'uncivilized' from someone else's perspective and vice versa, and that both are simply 'different' in some aspects and 'alike' in other aspects. Learners thus reflect on and are engaged in a conscious comparison of their own values and attitudes with different ones, in order to better realize how they construct 'the other'.

- Analysis: Behind similarities and differences, there are explanations for the practices, the values and the beliefs which many people of a particular cultural affiliation may share. Facilitators can support their learners in the analysis of what may lie beneath what they can see others doing and saying. This can be achieved, for example, by careful discussion and analysis, through inquiry based methods, of written or audio/video sources. The analysis can then be reflected back on the learners so that they may question their own practices, values and beliefs.

- Reflection: Comparison, analysis and experience need to be accompanied by time and space for reflection and the development of critical awareness and understanding. Facilitators, especially in non-formal and formal education, need to ensure that such time and space is provided in a deliberate and planned way. For example, teachers may ask students to discuss their experiences, encourage students to keep a logbook to keep track of their learning, and write or draw or share or otherwise respond to what they have learnt; but parents may also sit quietly with their children to talk about an experience.

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